

Satra and Women: Striving for equilibrium between conventionality and inclusiveness.

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”One of the best ways to understand the spirit of a civilization and to appreciate its excellence and to realize its limitation is the study of the history of position and status of women in it”- Altekhar.

The scenario before the rise of Neo-Vaishnavism in Assam was pre-occupied with child marriage, sati, tantrism, and sacrificial ritualism where the ultimate God for women was her husband, and as a result, being devotional and worshipping another male deity was also seen as a sin for women. The teachings of radical religious ‘guru’, Srimanta Sankardeva, and others are known for offering a better status to women of Assamese society. However, the attention of numerous individuals was drawn by the recent discussion surrounding the issue of women’s access to the sacred space within the Satra Institution.

The objective of this paper is to examine the historical context of the emergence of the Satra Institution in Assam and its stance in dealing with any challenges related to religious beliefs that hinder the attainment of gender equality.